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EFFECT OF VERMICOMPOST AND VERMIWASH OF BEEDI LEAF WASTE OF *EISENIA FOETIDA* ON PLANT GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

In the present study the vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia Fetida* was collected from department of Microbiology, Scott Christen College (Autonomous), Nagercoil-3 and the seed of Lady's Finger, Brinjal, chilly, were collected from farm house, Trivandrum. Effect of vermicompost on the growth of Lady's finger plant was studied for 90 days. The growth parameter such as Shoot length, Leaf width, Leaf height, Total number of leaf, foliage, Buds, Branches, Flower, Fruits. Were observed recorded and tabulated for every 30 days after sowing the seed (30th day, 60th day, 90th day). The maximum growth parameter were observed in the treatment supplemented with 100% of vermicompost. Effect of vermicompost on the growth of Brinjal plant was studied for 90 days. The growth parameter such as Shoot length, Leaf width, Leaf height, Total number of leaf, foliage, Buds, Branches, Flower, Fruits were observed recorded and tabulated for every 30 days after sowing the seed (30th day, 60th day, 90th day). The maximum growth parameter were observed in the treatment supplemented with 100% of vermicompost. Effect of vermiwash on the seed germination and of chilly seed were observed recorded and tabulated for every 30 days after sowing the seed (30th day, 60th day, 90th day) The maximum growth parameter were observed in the treatment supplemented with 60% vermiwash. The microbial population in the vermicompost of beedi leaf waste of *Eisenia fetida* was enumerated and tabulated. Total Heterotrophic Bacteria population of phosphate solubilizing microbes population and third place goes to *Azospirillum*. The microbial population in the vermiwash of beedi leaf waste of *Eisenia fetida* was enumerated and tabulated total heterotrophic bacteria population Actinomycetes population and third place goes to Phosphate solubilizing population.

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INTRODUCTION

In India agriculture and vegetation plays a vital role in its economy. The quality and value of agricultural organic soil amendments are often measured in terms of their contributions on nutrient supplies and soil fertility (Arancon *et al.*, 2006). The cost of inorganic fertilizers is very high and sometimes it is not available in the market for which the farmers fail to apply the inorganic fertilizers to the crop field in optimum time. On the other hand, the organic manure is easily available to the farmers and its cost is low compared to that of inorganic fertilizers (Alam *et al.*, 2007).

Vermicomposting is a process of bio-oxidation and stabilization of organic wastes and by the joint action of earthworms and microorganisms and the end product is called vermicompost. Vermicompost is also called as vermicompost or worm castings or worm humus or worm manure. The length of the maturation phase is not fixed and depends on the efficiency with which the active phase of the process takes place, which in turn is determined by the species and density of earthworm and the rate at which the residue is applied (Dominquez *et al.*, 2010).

Figure 1. Vermicompost.

Vermicompost is ideal organic manure for better growth and yield of many plants due to higher nutritional value than traditional composts. This is due to increased rate of mineralization and degree of humification by the action of earthworms. Vermicompost has also high porosity, aeration, drainage, and water holding capacity. Presence of microbiota particularly fungi, bacteria and actinomycetes makes it suitable for plant growth. Nutrients, such as nitrates, phosphates, and exchangeable calcium and soluble potassium in plant-available forms are present in vermicompost. Plant growth regulators and other plant growth influencing materials produced by microorganisms are also present (Joshi *et al.*, 2015).

Vermicompost contains plant nutrients including N, P, K, Ca, Mg, S, Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu and B, the uptake of which has a positive effect on plant nutrition, photosynthesis, the chlorophyll content of the leaves and improves the nutrient content of the different plant components (roots, shoots and the fruits). The high percentage of humic acids in vermicompost contributes to plant health, as it promotes the synthesis of phenolic compounds such as anthocyanins and flavonoids which may improve the plant quality and act as a deterrent to pests and diseases (Theunissen *et al.*, 2010).

Vermiwash is a liquid extract of organic waste material, which is collected after the passage of water through the different layers of earthworm culture units. Vermiwash is used as a liquid major nutritive and enzymatic element for promoting growth of all green plants. Vermiwash, the extracted body fluid of earthworms is also nutrient rich with components promoting good plant growth (Khaing *et al.*, 2008; GorakhNath *et al.*, 2012; Abdullah and Kumar Sukhraj, 2010).

Figure 2. Vermiwash.

Vermiwash is a liquid that is collected after the passage of water through a column of worm action. It is a mixture of excretory products and mucus secretion of earthworms along with micronutrient from the soil organic molecules. It is very useful as a foliar spray. These are transported to the leaf, shoots and other parts of the plants in the natural ecosystem. Vermiwash contains various enzymes and microbes. These are beneficial for growth and development of plant. The vermiwash also contains enzymes and secretion of earthworms and would stimulate the growth and yield of crops (Zambare *et al.*, 2008).

In the present study is on the effect of vermicompost and vermiwash on plant growth and determination of the microbiological characters of vermicompost and vermiwash used in the study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Seeds of vegetables namely lady's finger, brinjal, chilly, were selected for the present investigation undergone for a period of December 2018 to March 2018.

Collection of seeds

Seeds were collected from Thanumalain Agency, Nagercoil, Manufactured by Farm house located in Tc21/1410,pooma, Nedumcaud,Karamana,Thiruvananthapuram ,Kerala-695002 (plate 1).

Plate 1. Seeds of Lady's finger ,Brinjal ,Chilly taken for the study.

4.2. Collection of vermicompost

Vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia foetida* was obtained from PG department of Microbiology, Scott Christian college (Autonomous), Nagercoil-629003(Plate 2).

Plate:2. Vermicompost of *Eisenia foetida* used in the study.

Experimental design to demonstrate the effect of vermicompost on plant growth

Thick polythene bags of 10kg capacity was individually filled with growth medium containing red soil along with supplemented substrate vermicompost (Table 1, Plate 4). Plants were raised during December 2018 to March 2018. Seeds of both brinjal (Eggplant) and lady's finger (Okra) were sown in separate triplicate bags as ten seeds per bag at a depth of 3 cm from the surface soil. The bags were watered twice daily (morning and evening) and placed under sunlight.

Table 1. Treatments with vermicompost supplemented growth medium for plant growth.

Treatment	Growth medium		Seeds Sown
	Substrate added (kg)	Supplement added (gm)	
T1	3kg red soil	750gm of vermicompost(25%)	Brinjal and Lady's finger
T2	3kg red soil	1500gm of vermicompost(50%)	Brinjal and Lady's finger
T3	3kg red soil	2250gm of vermicompost(75%)	Brinjal and Lady's finger
T4	3kg red soil	3000gm of vermicompost(100%)	Brinjal and Lady's finger
Control	3kg red soil	-	Brinjal and Lady's finger

Collection of Vermiwash

A plastic barrel tub of 1 m height and 75cm bottom and top diameter was fitted with a gate-valve to facilitate drainage of eluates. The tub was filled to height of 25 cm with gravel above which was placed a layer of coarse sand (30 cm) and garden soil (30 cm). Above the soil, a layer of shade dried and powdered cow dung was added. Then gently moistened with water and the excess water was drained off. The unit was moistened and 250 healthy adult earthworm adults belonging to the species *Eisenia foetida* were released. After sixteen days, eluate was collected daily by slowly sprinkling five liters of water from the top. The water slowly percolated carrying with it nutrients from freshly formed castings, as well as washing through the filter unit. After 10 days enough amount of light yellow color vermiwash was collected (Ansari, 2008). (Plate 3).

Plate:3. Collection of Vermiwash.

Experimental design to demonstrate the effect of vermiwash on plant growth

Thick polythene bags of 5kg capacity was individually filled with growth medium containing red soil along with supplemented substrate vermiwash (Table 2) (plate 4). Plants were raised from December 2018 to March 2018. Seeds of chilli were sown in separate triplicate bags as ten seeds per bag at a depth of 3 cm from the surface soil. The bags were treated with vermiwash once in every 15 days. The bags were watered twice daily (morning and evening) and placed under sunlight.

Table 2. Treatments with vermiwash supplemented growth medium for plant growth.

Treatment	Growth medium		Seeds sown
	Substrate added(kg)	Supplement added (%)	
T1	3kg red soil	40 ml vermiwash +60 ml water (40%)	Chilly
T2	3kg red soil	50 ml vermiwash +50 ml water (50%)	Chilly
T3	3kg red soil	60 ml vermiwash +40 ml water (60%)	Chilly
Control	3kg red soil	Water 100%	Chilly

Plate 4 . Experimental set up to demonstrate the effect of vermicompost and vermiwash supplemented plant growth

Observation and measurement of plant growth parameters supplemented with vermicompost

Observation namely percentage of germination, shoot length, number of branches, number of leaves, number of buds, number of flower and yield after 30,60,90 days after planting were recorded using centimeter scale.

Observation of germination and growth parameters of seeds supplemented with vermiwash

Observation namely plant height, length of internode, number of leaves, number of branches, leaf surface were measured using a centimeter scale and recorded.

Microbial analysis of vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida***Enumeration of total heterotrophic bacteria**

The sample (1gm) vermicompost was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Nutrient agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Enumeration of fungi

The sample (1gm) vermicompost was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Rose Bengal agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at room temperature for 3 days.

Enumeration of phosphate solubilizing microbes

The sample (1gm) vermicompost was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Pikovskaya's agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Enumeration of nitrogen fixing bacteria

The sample (1gm) vermicompost was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Yeast Extract Mannitol agar medium (YEMA) (for *Rhizobium* sp.) Malate medium (for *Azospirillum* sp.) and Ashby's Mannitol agar medium (for *Azotobacter* sp.) and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 -96hours.

Enumeration of cellulose degrading bacteria

The sample (1gm) vermicompost was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Cellulose Congo-Red agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48hours.

Enumeration of Actinomycetes

The sample (1gm) vermicompost was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Kenknight's agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 28°C for 7 days.

Microbial analysis of vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida***Enumeration of total heterotrophic bacteria**

The sample (1ml)verminwash was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Nutrient agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Enumeration of fungi

The sample (1ml) vermiwash was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Rose Bengal agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at room temperature for 3 days.

Enumeration of phosphate solubilizing Microbes

The sample (1ml) vermiwash was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Pikovskaya's agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Enumeration of nitrogen fixing bacteria

The sample(1ml) vermiwash was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Yeast Extract Mannitol agar medium (YEMA) (for *Rhizobium* sp.) Malate medium (for *Azospirillum* sp.)and Ashby's Mannitol agar medium (for *Azotobacter* sp.)and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 -96hours.

Enumeration of cellulose degrading bacteria

The sample (1ml) vermiwash was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Cellulose Congo-red agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48hours.

Enumeration of Actinomycetes

The sample (1ml) vermiwash was serially diluted and plated by agar pour plating technique. 1ml of the each of the dilution of 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} were plated in sterile Kenknight's agar medium and one plate served as control. For each dilution original and duplicate plates were maintained. The plates were incubated at 28°C for 7 days.

RESULTS

Microbial analysis of vermicompost of *Eisenia fetida*

Enumeration of total heterotrophic bacteria

The bacterial count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Nutrient agar medium. After overnight incubation colonies were observed. The colony count was determined both manually and also with a colony counter and the colony count (cfu/gm) was tabulated (Table 3) (Plate 5A).

Table 3. Enumeration of total heterotrophic bacteria from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/gm		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10^4	260	240	250
2	10^5	135	128	131.5
3	10^6	87	80	83.5

The number of colonies per gm of the sample was calculated by taking any one of the dilution into consideration by using formula,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Number of colonies/gm of the sample} &= \frac{\text{Number of colonies}}{\text{volume of the sample plated}} \times \text{Dilution factor} \\ &= \frac{250}{1} \times 10^4 \\ &= 250 \times 10^4 \text{ CFU/gm} \end{aligned}$$

Enumeration of fungi

The fungal colony count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Rose Bengal agar medium. After incubation at 28°C for 3-5 days colonies were observed. The colony count was determined by macroscopic observation and tabulated (Table) (Plate 5B).

Table:4. Enumeration of fungi from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/gm		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10^4	248	230	239
2	10^5	160	155	157.5
3	10^6	95	90	92.5

Enumeration of phosphate solubilizing microbes

The phosphate solubilizing microbial count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in pikovaskaya's agar medium. After incubation at 28°C for 7 days clear zone was formed around the colonies. The colony count was determined by both manual counting and colony counter and tabulated (Table 5) (Plate 6-A).

Table 5. Enumeration of phosphate solubilizing microbes from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/gm		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10^4	253	240	246.5
2	10^5	15	16	15.5
3	10^6	3	0	1.5

Enumeration of nitrogen fixing bacteria.

The nitrogen fixing bacterial colony count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Yest Extract Mannitol agar (YEMA) medium (for *Rhizobium* sp.) Malate medium (for *Azospirillum* sp.) and Ashbys Mannitol agar (for *Azotobacter* sp.) was used. After incubation at 37°C for 3 days the colonies were observed.

Enumeration of *Rhizobium* sp.

Rhizobium sp. count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Yest Extract Mannitol agar (YEMA) medium. After incubation at 25°C - 30°C for 4 days colonies were observed gummy and soft colonies, were observed, counted and, Tabulated (Table 6 (Plate 6-B)).

Table 6 Enumeration of *Rhizobium* sp from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/gm		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	220	208	214
2	10 ⁵	167	155	161
3	10 ⁶	80	74	77

Enumeration of *Azotobacter* sp.

Azotobacter sp.count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eiseniafetidaby* serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Ashby's Mannitol agar medium. After incubation at 28⁰ c for 96 hours the colonies were observed as oval colonies tabulated(Table 7) (Plate 7-A).

Table: 7. Enumeration of *Azotobacter* sp. from vermicompost of beedi leaf wsate by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/gm		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	250	240	245
2	10 ⁵	180	178	179
3	10 ⁶	80	78	79

Enumeration of *Azospirillum* sp.

Azospirillum.colony count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eiseniafetidaby* serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Malate medium. After incubation at 28⁰ c for 48 hours the colonies were observed flat, soft, milky, white mucoid colonies were observed, counted tabulated(Table 8) (Plate 7-B).

Table 8. Enumeration of *Azospirillum* sp.from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/mg		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	232	230	231
2	10 ⁵	170	165	167.5
3	10 ⁶	82	78	80

Enumeration of cellulose degrading bacteria

The cellulose degrading bacteria count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique. After incubation clear zone was formed around the colonies. The colony was determined by both manual counting and colony counter and tabulated (Table9) (Plate 8- B).

Table 9. Enumeration of Cellulose degrading bacteria from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/gm		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	220	217	218.5
2	10 ⁵	167	155	161
3	10 ⁶	80	74	77

Enumeration of Actinomycetes

The Actinomycetes count was determined from the vermicompost of *Eisenia fetidaby* serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Kenknight's agar medium. After incubation at 28⁰ c for 7 days the colonies was observed in powdery form the colony was determined by manual counting and by colony counter recorded tabulated (Table 10) (Plate 8-A).

Table 10. Enumeration of Actinomycetes from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/gm		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	243	240	241
2	10 ⁵	143	132	137
3	10 ⁶	92	86	89

Microbial analysis of vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida*

Enumeration of total heterotrophic bacteria

The bacterial count was determined from the vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Nutrient agar medium. After overnight incubation colonies were observed. The colony count was determined both manually and also with a colony counter and the colony count (cfu/ml) was tabulated (Table 11) (Plate 9-A).

Table 11. Enumeration of total heterotrophic bacteria from vermiwash of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	260	250	255
2	10 ⁵	145	135	40
3	10 ⁶	98	86	922

Enumeration of fungi

The fungal colony count was determined from the vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Rose Bengal agar medium. After incubation at 28^oc for 3-5 days colony were observed. The colony count was determined by macroscopic observation and tabulated (Table 12) (Plate 9-B)

Table 12. Enumeration of fungi from vermiwash of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	150	155	152.5
2	10 ⁵	90	86	88
3	10 ⁶	62	56	59

Enumeration of phosphate solubilizing microbes

The phosphate solubilizing microbial count was determined from the vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in pikovaskaya's agar medium. After incubation at 28^oc for 7 days clear zone was formed around the colonies. The colony count was determined by both manual counting and colony counter and tabulated (Table 13) (Plate-10-A).

Table 13. Enumeration of phosphate solubilizing microbes from verminwash of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	220	210	215
2	10 ⁵	176	166	171
3	10 ⁶	98	86	92

The number of colonies per ml of the sample was calculated by taking any one of the dilution into consideration by using formula,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Number of colonies/ml of the sample} &= \frac{\text{Number of colonies}}{\text{volume of the sample plated}} \times \text{Dilution factor} \\ &= \frac{215}{1} \times 10^4 \\ &= 215 \times 10^5 \text{ CFU/ml} \end{aligned}$$

Enumeration of nitrogen fixing bacteria.

The nitrogen fixing bacterial colony count was determined from the vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Yest Extract Mannitol agar (YEMA) medium (for *Rhizobium* sp.) Malate medium (for *Azospirillum* sp.) and Ashbys Mannitol ager (for *Azotobacter* sp.) was used. After incubation at 37^o for 3 days the colonies were observed.

Enumeration of *Rhizobium* sp.

Rhizobium sp. count was determined from the vermiwash of *Eisenia foetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Yest Extract Mannitol agar (YEMA) medium. After incubation at 25^o-30^o c for 4 days colonies were observed gummy and soft look colonies, Enumerated and Tabulated (Table 14) (Plate 10-B).

Table 14. Enumeration of *Rhizobium* sp from vermiwash of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	195	182	188.5
2	10 ⁵	92	86	89.76
3	10 ⁶	75	66	70.5

Enumeration of *Azotobacter* sp.

Azotobacter sp. count was determined from the vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Ashby's Mannitol agar medium. After incubation at 28⁰ c for 96 hours the colonies were observed as oval colonies tabulated (Table 15) (Plate 11-A).

Table 15. Enumeration of *Azotobacter* sp. from vermiwash of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	120	140	130
2	10 ⁵	88	78	83
3	10 ⁶	52	45	48.5

Enumeration of *Azospirillum* sp.

Azospirillum sp colony count was determined from the vermiwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Malate medium. After incubation at 28⁰ c for 48 hours the flate, soft, milky, white mucoid colonies were observed, counted and tabulated (Table 16) (Plate 11-B).

Table 16. Enumeration of *Azospirillum* sp from vermiwash of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	210	202	206
2	10 ⁵	95	84	89.5
3	10 ⁶	56	44	50

Enumeration of cellulose degrading bacteria

The cellulose degrading bacteria count was determined from the verminwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique. After incubation clear zone was formed around the colonies. The colony was determined by in both manual counting and colony counter and tabulate (Table 16) (Plate 12-B).

Table 16. Enumeration of cellulose degrading bacteria from vermiwash of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	155	167	161
2	10 ⁵	84	74	79
3	10 ⁶	64	52	58

Enumeration of Actinomycetes

The Actinomycetes count was determined from the verminwash of *Eisenia fetida* by serial dilution and agar pour plating technique in Kenknight's agar medium. After incubation at 28⁰ c for 7 days the colonies was observed in powdery form. The colony was count determined by manual counting and by colony counter, recorded and tabulated (Table 16) (Plate 12-A).

Table 16. Enumeration of Actinomycetes from vermicompost of beedi leaf waste by *Eisenia fetida*.

S.NO	Dilution	Cfu/ml		Average
		Original	Duplicate	
1	10 ⁴	253	240	246.5
2	10 ⁵	115	116	115.5
3	10 ⁶	96	86	92

Measurement of growth parameter of vermicompost and vermiwash supplemented plants

The growth parameter of vermicompost and vermiwash supplemented plants were determined recorded and tabulated on 30th 60th 90th days of planting or sowing the seed (Table. 16, 17,18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 24, 25) (Figure. 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11) (Plate.13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21).

Figure -3. Growth parameters of Brinjal plant supplemented with vermicompost (After 30 days).

Figure – 4. Growth parameters of Lady's finger plant supplemented with vermicompost (After 30 days).

Figure- 5. Growth parameters of chilly plant supplemented with vermiwash (After 30 days).

Figure – 6.Growth parameter of Brinjal plant supplemented with vermicompost (After 60 days).

Figure- 7. Growth parameters of Lady's finger plant supplemented with vermicompost (After 60 days).

Figure – 8. Growth parameters of chilly supplemented withvermiwash (After 60 days).

Figure – 9.Growth parameters of Brinjalplant supplemented with vermicompost (After 90 days).

Figure – 10. Growth parameters of Lady's finger plant supplemented with vermicompost(After 90 days).

Figure-11. Growth parameters of Chilly plant supplemented with vermiwash (After 90 days).

DISCUSSION

Vermicomposting is a decomposition process involving the joint action of earthworms and microorganisms. Although microorganisms are responsible for the biochemical degradation of organic matter, earthworms are crucial drivers of the process, by fragmenting and conditioning the substrate and dramatically altering its biological activity (Dominguez and Edwards, 2010). Vermicompost produced by the activity of earthworms is rich in macro and micronutrients, vitamins, growth hormones, enzymes such as proteases, amylases, lipase, cellulose and chitinase and immobilized microflora. The enzymes continue to disintegrate organic matter even after they have been ejected from the worms (Bariket *et al.*, 2011).

In the present study, Vermiwash is liquid manure that has been reported to have excellent growth promoting effects besides serving as biopesticides even though much work has been done on vermicomposting only few reports are available on vermiwash and its impact on the plant growth (Hattiet *et al.*, 2010). Vermiwash is a watery extract of vermicompost, extracted in the presence of rich population of earthworms and contains several enzymes, plant growth hormones, vitamins along with micro and macronutrients which increases the resistance power of crops against various diseases and enhances the growth and productivity of crops (Zambare *et al.*, 2008).

The increasing trend of abundant use of inorganic fertilizers along with herbicides and pesticides and exploiting available water resources etc, in the present agriculture system poses a great threat to the sustainability of our agro-ecosystem. Under such situation it is essential to look for alternatives which are effective and eco-friendly. Now we are on the way of search of organic biofertilizer such as vermicompost and vermiwash.

Zambare *et al.* (2008) reported that vermiwash contain nitrogen fixing bacteria like *Azotobactersp.* and *Rhizombiumsp.*, which make the inorganic nitrogen and amino acid available to plants. Microbiological study of vermiwashreveated that it contain nitrogen high amount of TotalHeterotrophic Bacteria,Nitrogen Fixing Bacteria like *Azospirillum sp.* and *Rhizombium sp.*

Vermiwash growth yield good plant tonic which can be used foliar spray. The coelomic fluid from earthworm body has antibacterial properties. Studies on effect of spraying of vermiwash on vegetable chilly indicated that quality and quantity of yield were improved markedly (Rakesh Joshi and Adarsh Palvig, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Thus the vrmicompost and vermiwash has growth nutritional and microbial potentials which may act as growth inducers by making the nutrient easily available to the plant roots. So the chemical fertilizer in the crop field that contributed greatly to the deterioration of the environment, loss of soil fertility, less agricultural productivity. Soil degradation can be avoided and instead the organic fertilizer namely vermicompost and vermiwsh can be used as te best option of agriculture that increases the soil fertility and there by increased agriculture productivity.

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